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Uncertainty evaluation of road traffic noise models in two Ibero-American cities --Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>In this study, the differences between calculated and measured noise values were evaluated in situ through more than 550 measurements in two Ibero-American cities. These categorisation method-based noise measurements were performed at 216 sampling points located on five different types of urban roads. Two different calculation methods were used for noise modelling—XPS 31-133 and CNOSSOS-EU. In addition to the magnitude and average of the uncertainties, their biases were evaluated independently in the calculation. These uncertainties were analysed overall for each city and considering the type of urban road. The relationship between road traffic characteristics (flow and percentage for each vehicle class) and the type of uncertainty was also studied. A high percentage of the uncertainties of both methods are lower than 3 dB in both cities. However, the calculation methods are different from each other in terms of the distribution of errors for the various types of urban roads and the bias of the estimates. The XPS 31-133 method provides the worst estimates for sound measurements performed on residential streets, whereas the CNOSSOS method presents the largest estimation errors on main streets. In terms of the bias, the XPS 31-133 method overestimates the noise values, primarily in residential streets; this overestimation is explained by the increase in the flow and percentage of medium heavy vehicles. On the other hand, the CNOSSOS-EU method underestimates the noise values in a high percentage of measurements performed on the various types of urban roads. This underestimation is significantly related to the increase in light vehicles flow.</p>
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Response to Reviewers:	<p>Reviewer #2</p> <p>I appreciate the work done by the authors to improve the quality of the paper. I strongly believe that the decision of converting it to a technical note is very sensible. There are some issues that needs further consideration (below).</p> <p>The authors would like to thank the reviewer for his/her comments and suggestions</p>

25 errors on main streets. In terms of the bias, the XPS 31-133 method overestimates the
26 noise values, primarily in residential streets; this overestimation is explained by the
27 increase in the flow and percentage of medium heavy vehicles. On the other hand, the
28 CNOSSOS-EU method underestimates the noise values in a high percentage of
29 measurements performed on the various types of urban roads. This underestimation is
30 significantly related to the increase in light vehicles flow.

31 **Keywords:** Noise mapping; uncertainty; road traffic.

32 **1. Introduction**

33 The strategic noise maps are the main tool for noise assessment and management
34 according the Environmental Noise Directive (END) [1]. There are different
35 methodologies for noise mapping but calculation methods are the most commonly used.
36 Some European Union Member States (EU MS) developed their own calculation
37 methods. For EU MS that have no national calculation methods or wish to change it, the
38 French national calculation method (NMPB-Routes-96/XPS 31-133) was recommended
39 for road traffic noise [1]. These methods have also been used and tested in non-European
40 countries [2–4] and in comparative studies between European and non-European cities
41 [5]. Noise exposure levels in non-European cities are relevant to the World Health
42 Organisation (WHO), as a large body of the evidence underpinning the recommendations
43 was derived not only from European noise effect studies but also from research in other
44 parts of the world [6]. Noise maps are available for agglomerations with more than
45 100,000 inhabitants in Europe. Noise pollution problems are also found in towns [7,8].

46 A wide range of calculation methods has been used cross-nationally, which has
47 prevented to evaluate noise exposure levels comparatively across all countries.
48 Consequently, the European Commission (EC) established that EU MS should use

49 common noise assessment methods (CNOSSOS-EU) in 2019 [9]. Implementing this
50 method in non-European countries would also contribute to the development of globally
51 common actions.

52 CNOSSOS-EU propagation models for road sources were developed from the
53 NMPB French model [10]. However, source models developed new emission values for
54 road vehicles. The CNOSSOS-EU method groups vehicles into five separate categories,
55 whereas only three are established in the NMPB/XPS 31-133 method. Some authors have
56 found inaccuracies in the sound power coefficients for road vehicles in the CNOSSOS-
57 EU method [11]. This methodology is to be applied for the next round of noise mapping
58 in 2022. It is therefore important to analyse their estimates in different urban
59 environments.

60 Calculation methods follow a rigorous validation process. However, road
61 characteristics sampled for validation may differ from urban roads [12]. The "Good
62 Practice Guidance for Strategic Noise Mapping and the Production of Associated Data
63 on Noise Exposure" (WG-AEN) [13] recommends *in situ* measurements to validate the
64 noise levels modelled by calculation methods. This validation is also considered as the
65 calibration of the computation models. There are current studies where the CNOSSOS-
66 EU method is validated in urban environments. However, the number of *in situ* sampling
67 points is very low and most of them are located on major urban roads [14,15]. Other
68 current studies compare the predictions of the CNOSSOS-EU method with other noise
69 models but no *in situ* measurements are performed [16,17].

70 The calibration of the calculation methods is essential because it is extremely difficult
71 to include all the elements and characteristics of the real environment that is being
72 modelled. Thus, some suppositions about building absorption, building height, vehicle
73 speed, ground region absorption, and other factors are commonly used in noise mapping.

74 These suppositions, commonly based on expert recommendations [13,18] or national
75 regulations, can introduce an uncertainty in the calculated noise values.

76 The first question that can arise when a change in the calculation method is
77 established is whether the results obtained using the two methods are similar; thus, a
78 comparison between the different methods is necessary. Comparing these two noise
79 mapping methods (CNOSSOS-EU and XPS 31-133) from the data reported in previous
80 studies is complicated because the input data required for both the methods is different.

81 Extensive measurements were conducted in this study, and data from more than 550
82 noise measurements were used to compare the uncertainties associated with the two
83 calculation methods. The magnitude and bias of the difference between the calculated and
84 measured noise levels were analysed. A total of 216 points were sampled in two cities
85 located in different Ibero-American countries (Spain and Chile). The sampling points
86 were located on different types of urban roads. Previous studies report less variability in
87 the sound levels and the characteristics of road traffic within each type of urban road
88 [3,19]. These variables were also related to the urban features of the streets [20].

89 The main objective of this study is to evaluate the difference between the measured
90 and calculated noise levels for two different calculation methods (XPS 31-133 and
91 CNOSSOS-EU) and to analyse some possible factors that cause this difference, such as
92 the type of street where the sampling point was located or the characteristics of the traffic
93 flow (number of vehicles, type of vehicles, and so on). The uncertainty bias (positive or
94 negative difference) was analysed independently because it could be related to different
95 sources. Application of the CNOSSOS-EU method in non-European countries and town
96 will also be analysed in this study.

97 **2. Methods**

98 *2.1. Cities studied*

99 The city of Talca is located in central Chile and has approximately 220,000
100 inhabitants but its population increases during the university's academic year. The active
101 population works mainly in the service and industrial sectors (approximately 55% and
102 36%, respectively). The mean annual temperature is 13 °C, whereas the mean annual
103 rainfall is 750 mm. Moraleja town is located in the region of Extremadura (Southwest of
104 Spain). It has a population of approximately 6,750 inhabitants. Most buildings have one
105 or two floors as in Talca. The mean annual temperature is 16 °C, whereas the mean
106 annual rainfall is 694 mm. Commerce and industry associated with the agricultural sector
107 is predominant in this town.

108 2.2. *Noise measurement procedure*

109 Urban roads were classified into different types according to the categorisation
110 method (see Fig. 1). Noise levels are expected to be significantly stratified in these road
111 types as shown in previous studies [7,21]. Sampling points were randomly located within
112 each urban road type.

113 a)

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115 b)

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117 **Fig. 1.** Road categories and sampling points in cities of (a) Talca and (b) Moraleja

118 Noise measurements were performed during daytime on working days in 2016 and
119 2018 in both the cities. Two or three 15-min measurements were performed at each
120 sampling point, at different daytime intervals and on different working days. The ISO
121 1996-2 guidelines were considered in the measurements [22]. A duration of 15 minutes
122 was established in the measurements because some urban roads registered a low flow of
123 vehicles [22]. This measurement duration has also been used in previous studies [23,24].
124 Class 1 sound-level meters were used (2250 and 2238 Brüel & Kjaer) and calibrated
125 before and after each measurement. The sound-level meter was located 1 m from the curb
126 and away from any reflective surface. The urban and road traffic characteristics were
127 also recorded. Thus, vehicle flows corresponding to the five categories defined by
128 CNOSSOS-EU method [9] were registered during the measurements.

129 In addition, other relevant information such as meteorological conditions, street
130 dimensions, road surface types, and conservation of the road surface was also registered.
131 Road traffic was the noise source considered for this study. Therefore, the measurement
132 was restarted when another noise source impacted the sound values.

133 *2.3. Noise modelling*

134 The Predictor v.11.20 software was used for noise mapping. The three-dimensional
135 models of the two cities are shown in Fig. S1.

136 The following configuration options was used for noise modelling:

- 137 • Number of reflections: 1
- 138 • Meteorological conditions: Default values of Toolkit 17 of the WG-AEN [13]
139 were considered. Probst [25] proved that it is not necessary to take into account
140 meteorological influences in the recommended calculation methods.
- 141 • Building height: Ground floor—4.5 m; each additional floor—3 m [26]

- 142 • Absorption of buildings and barriers: Reflective
- 143 • Flow type: Constant flow
- 144 • Vehicles speed: Maximum speed allowed for each street.

145 The receiver points were located in noise model at the same position where *in situ*
146 measurement was carried out. For this purpose, photographs were captured during the
147 sampling. A total of 555 sound measurements were estimated with calculation methods.

148 Road traffic flow and category was registered on the urban roads during the sound
149 measurements. The mean value of the flow of each vehicle type was assigned for the
150 non-sampled nearby streets considering the type of road category.

151 2.4. Statistical analysis

152 A descriptive and inferential analysis was performed on the differences between the
153 sound levels calculated by the noise method ($L_{eq-method}$) and those measured *in situ* (L_{eq-}
154 measurement). The statistical parameters of centralisation, dispersion, and shape were
155 obtained from these differences or uncertainties to obtain as much information as possible
156 about the accuracy of the noise methods. These parameters were calculated for all the
157 measurements performed in the city and for each road category.

158 The distribution of the uncertainties did not differ significantly from a normal
159 distribution ($p > 0.05$ according to the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test); therefore, parametric
160 tests were conducted for the inferential analysis. Average values of the uncertainties in
161 both the methods were compared using the *t*-test. In addition, the paired *t*-test was used
162 to determine the significance of the uncertainty bias. Finally, the relationships between
163 the uncertainties and road traffic characteristics were analysed (Pearson's *r*). In this
164 analysis, uncertainties were differentiated according to their bias.

- 165 – Positive error: $L_{eq-method} (dBA) > L_{eq-measurement} (dBA)$
- 166 – Negative error: $L_{eq-measurement} (dBA) > L_{eq-method} (dBA)$

167 The variables associated with the source of the noise from the road traffic analysed
168 were: $\log(Q_L)$, $\log(Q_H)$, $\log(Q_{mh})$, $\log(Q_{hd})$, $\log(Q_M)$, $\log(Q_{ma})$, $\log(Q_{mb})$, $\%Q_L$, $\%Q_H$,
169 $\%Q_{mh}$, $\%Q_{hd}$, $\%Q_M$, $\%Q_{ma}$, and $\%Q_{mb}$, where $\log Q$ is the decimal logarithm of the
170 vehicle flow, $\%$ represents the percentage of vehicles, L denotes light motor vehicles
171 (Category 1 in END [9]), H denotes heavy vehicles (Categories 2 and 3 in [9]), mh
172 represents medium heavy vehicles (Category 2 in [9]), hd represents heavy duty vehicles
173 (Category 3 in [9]), M indicates powered two-wheelers (Category 4 in [9]), ma indicates
174 mopeds (Category 4a in [9]), and mb indicates motorcycles (Category 4b in [9]).

175 The correct interpretation of the results obtained for the relationship between the sign
176 of the uncertainty and the correlation coefficient is the following:

- 177 – Positive error and positive correlation coefficient: The overestimation error
178 increases with increasing flow or percentage of road traffic and percentage.
- 179 – Positive error and negative correlation coefficient: The overestimation error
180 decreases with increasing flow or percentage of road traffic.
- 181 – Negative error and positive correlation coefficient: The underestimation error
182 decreases with increasing flow or percentage of road traffic.
- 183 – Negative error and negative correlation coefficient: The underestimation error
184 increases with increasing flow or percentage of road traffic.

185 **3. Results and discussion**

186 *3.1. Analysis of the noise modelling mapping uncertainty*

187 The difference between the sound level estimated by the calculation method (XPS
188 31-133 or CNOSSOS-EU) and the sound level measured *in situ* was analysed. This
189 difference, $L_{eq-method} - L_{eq-measure}$ (dBA), was referred to as noise modelling uncertainty.
190 Average values of $L_{eq-method} - L_{eq-measured}$ (dBA) are shown in Table 1 and 2.

191 **Table 1**

192 Average values and percentages of differences between calculated and measured sound
 193 levels in Talca city.

	Overall	Urban road category					
		1	2	3	4	5	
XPS 31-133	Average value ±	0.78 ±	-0.92 ±	0.05 ±	-0.06 ±	0.89 ±	1.56 ±
	standard deviation	2.22	1.51	2.12	1.48	2.37	2.21
	Average value ±	1.86 ±	1.49 ±	1.77 ±	1.19 ±	2.06 ±	2.11 ±
	standard deviation (absolute values)	1.44	0.92	1.13	0.87	1.46	1.69
	Percentage between 0 and 3 dB	80.05	91.67	89.74	94.67	74.77	72.37
CNOSSOS-EU	Average value ±	-1.68 ±	-3.65 ±	-3.03 ±	-2.72 ±	-1.89 ±	-0.36 ±
	standard deviation	2.16	1.62	1.82	1.34	1.77	2.13
	Average value ±	2.28 ±	3.65 ±	3.03 ±	2.73 ±	2.13 ±	1.76 ±
	standard deviation (absolute values)	1.51	1.62	1.82	1.32	1.47	1.25
	Percentage between 0 and 3 dB	69.33	29.17	51.28	56.00	72.07	84.87

194 **Table 2**

195 Average values and percentages of differences between calculated and measured sound
 196 levels in Moraleja town.

	Overall	Urban road category					
		1	2	3	4	5	
XPS 31-133	Average value ±	0.97 ±	1.88 ±	0.69 ±	0.94 ±	1.29 ±	0.38 ±
	standard deviation	2.54	1.30	1.21	2.46	2.88	2.96
	Average value ±	2.04 ±	1.94 ±	1.18 ±	1.85 ±	2.38 ±	2.30 ±
	standard deviation (absolute values)	1.78	1.21	0.70	1.87	2.05	1.86
	Percentage between 0 and 3 dB	74.03	77.78	100	75.00	65.00	70.00
CNOSSOS-EU	Average value ±	-2.43 ±	-3.21 ±	-3.54 ±	-2.04 ±	-2.07 ±	-2.41 ±
	standard deviation	1.89	1.62	1.41	1.85	1.90	2.01

Average value ± standard deviation (absolute values)	2.67 ± 1.53	3.21 ± 1.62	3.54 ± 1.41	2.21 ± 1.63	2.38 ± 1.48	2.84 ± 1.31
Percentage between 0 and 3 dB	62.34	38.89	37.50	80.00	75.00	57.50

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Considering overall sound measurements (see Tables 1 and 2), average absolute value of the uncertainty in both methods is close to 2 dB, which is considered as high accuracy by the WG-AEN [13]. This guide recommends that the noise modelling uncertainties should not exceed 5 dB. The average values obtained for the overall measurements are corroborated by the high percentage of differences of less than 3 dB between the two cities. These percentages are higher than those obtained in previous studies [3,4,27]. Therefore, both methods are suitable for noise mapping in non-European countries and in small cities.

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Considering the average absolute values obtained in urban road categories (see Tables 1 and 2), there are differences in the trend between the two calculation methods. The uncertainties increase their average value and standard deviation from the noisiest urban roads to the quietest ones for the XPS method. The opposite phenomenon occurs for the CNOSSOS-EU method. Suárez et al. [28] and Bertellino et al. [14] also observed a decrease in the uncertainties in the noise models on urban roads that registered a higher flow of road traffic. Bertellino et al. [14] and Guarnaccia et al. [29] found that the uncertainties obtained using the CNOSSOS-EU method were similar to other calculation methods for urban roads with sound levels of approximately 55 dBA.

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The urban roads that registered the highest flow of vehicles (Categories 1 and 2) present uncertainties, with the absolute average values exceeding 3 dB in the CNOSSOS-EU method. However, the uncertainties in the XPS method do not exceed 2 dB for these road categories. These results lead to significant differences between the two methods in

220 their estimates on these urban roads (see Table 3). Both calculation methods generate
 221 similar average errors (1.8 to 2.8 dB) for urban roads in residential use (Categories 4 and
 222 5). Category 3, urban service road, indicates differences between the two cities. The
 223 measured noise levels are high for Category 3 in Talca, whereas they are closer to those
 224 recorded for residential urban roads in Moraleja. The average errors obtained using both
 225 methods present significant differences for Category 3 in Talca, but these differences are
 226 not significant in Moraleja.

227 **Table 3**

228 Comparison of absolute average errors between XPS 31-133 and CNOSSOS-EU (*t*-test).

229

Talca		Moraleja	
Category	<i>p</i>-value	Category	<i>p</i>-value
1	<0.001	1	<0.05
2	<0.001	2	<0.001
3	<0.001	3	>0.05
4	>0.05	4	>0.05
5	>0.05	5	>0.05

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231 The uncertainties in both the calculation methods differ depending on the type of
 232 urban road. Although the estimates obtained from both the methods are accurate, these
 233 errors can exceed 3 dB on urban roads with high road traffic flow for the case of the
 234 CNOSSOS method. This result implies that the errors of the main urban roads only
 235 should not be analysed, as the highest percentage of the population lives on residential
 236 roads [30]. Although both methods present low average uncertainties for residential
 237 roads, the variability in these values is high for these road categories (see Tables 1 and
 238 2).

239 Considering the bias of the noise estimates, it can be seen that the average differences
240 obtained using the XPS 31-133 model are mostly positive, which indicates that the
241 calculated values are greater than the measured values, whereas the average differences
242 obtained using the CNOSSOS-EU model are negative, which indicates the contrary case.
243 The average values for the overall measurements in both cities are significantly different
244 with respect to zero according to the paired *t*-test ($p < 0.01$). These results are
245 corroborated by the shape of the uncertainly distributions shown in Fig. S2. Although the
246 distributions of the differences present a similar shape for both cities and models, the
247 differences obtained using the CNOSSOS model clearly tend toward negative values and
248 those obtained using the XPS 31-133 model tend slightly toward positive values.

249 The trend of average uncertainties in the different urban road categories is similar to
250 that obtained for the overall measurements (Tables 2 and 3). However, the positive bias
251 of the XPS 31-133 method is less pronounced. Thus, the averages of the differences
252 obtained between Categories 2 and 3 in Talca and between Categories 2 and 5 in Moraleja
253 are close to zero. These average values do not even present significant differences with
254 respect to zero according to the paired *t*-test. The average uncertainties obtained using
255 the CNOSSOS-EU method and its absolute values are similar, indicating that almost all
256 the uncertainties are negative.

257 The percentages of negative differences obtained for overall measurements using the
258 XPS 31-133 model were 35.41% and 34.42% in the cities of Talca and Moraleja,
259 respectively. These percentages were 79.55% and 91.56% for the CNOSSOS-EU model.
260 Considering these results, it can be concluded that the XPS 31-133 model tends to
261 overestimate the noise levels and the CNOSSOS-EU model underestimates them. Morley
262 et al. [31], Khan et al. [16], Bertellino et al. [14], and Guarnaccia et al. [29] also indicated
263 the underestimation of the sound levels in the CNOSSOS-EU method. However, the

264 other previous calculation methods—RLS-90 [3,4], CRTN [31,32], RTN-96 [16], ISO
265 9613-1/2 [33,34], and XPS 31-133 [14,35]—tend to overestimate the sound levels. These
266 results may generate discrepancies in the selection of the calculation method. In previous
267 studies, some authors have pointed out that, from a preventive point of view [3,36], an
268 overestimation of sound levels is preferable. The uncertainties associated with the
269 calculation models also impact the estimates of the effects of noise on health [37].

270 The estimates from both noise methods exhibit a similar trend for both cities despite
271 their different location and size. This is an interesting result for the worldwide application
272 of these calculation methods. The average error and percentage of error between 0 and 3
273 dB are slightly higher in Moraleja than in Talca. The lower flow of road traffic recorded
274 in the road categories of Moraleja are impacted by this higher uncertainty in the
275 calculation models. Similar results have been obtained in other cities of different
276 population sizes [3,28].

277 *3.2. Relationship between noise modelling uncertainty and road traffic characteristics*

278 Road traffic is the main source of noise in urban environments. Fig. 2 shows the
279 relationship between the equivalent sound level and the logarithm of the road traffic flow
280 recorded in the measurements performed in this study. Only road traffic flow explains
281 91% and 83% of the equivalent variability in sound level. Therefore, the variables
282 associated with the sound source explain the sound levels present in urban roads to a
283 significant extent. For this reason, the relationships between the uncertainties in the
284 calculation models and the variables associated with road traffic were analysed. The
285 urban road categories are also differentiated in Figure 2. The average sound levels of
286 these categories were significantly stratified (except between Category 1 and 2 in
287 Moraleja). Therefore, the analysis of the relationship between noise modelling
288 uncertainty and road traffic characteristics was carried out for each road category.

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293 **Fig. 2.** Relationship between equivalent sound level and road traffic flow in (a) Talca and
294 (b) Moraleja

295 The negative errors (the calculated values are lower than the measured values, and,
296 thus, there is an underestimation in the calculation model) and positive errors (the
297 calculated values are higher than the measured values, and, thus, there is an
298 overestimation in the calculation model) were analysed independently. Differentiating in
299 terms of the sign of uncertainty provides more information on the source of errors [38].
300 With respect to the variables associated with road traffic, the flow and percentages of the
301 categories of vehicles proposed by the END were considered [1,9]—light motor vehicles,

302 heavy vehicles, medium heavy vehicles, heavy duty vehicles, powered two-wheelers,
 303 i.e., mopeds and motorcycles.

304 As mentioned earlier, the sign of the error and the correlation coefficient (Pearson's
 305 r) must be considered to correctly interpret the results. The results obtained using the
 306 XPS 31-133 and CNOSSOS-EU methods are presented in Tables 4 and 5 and Table 6,
 307 respectively.

308 As illustrated, the XPS method tends to overestimate the sound levels. However, this
 309 bias is slight and not even significant in certain categories. Table 4 presents the
 310 relationships among the positive errors obtained using the XPS 31-133 method
 311 (overestimation) and the road traffic variables. This was an overall analysis that was
 312 performed for all the estimated sound values in the cities, by differentiating based on the
 313 road category.

314 **Table 4**

315 Relationships among positive uncertainties in XPS 31-133 method and flow of various
 316 vehicle types recorded under each type of road category

Pearson's r	Variable 1: Positive Error												
	Road categories in Talca						Road categories in Moraleja						
	1	2	3	4	5	Overall	1	2	3	4	5	Overall	
$\log(Q_L)$	-	-	-	-0.33**	-	-0.30***	-	-	-	-	-	-	-0.20*
$\log(Q_H)$	-	0.66***	-	0.54***	-	-	0.49*	-	-	-	-	-	-0.52***
$\log(Q_{mh})$	-	0.74***	-	0.46***	-	-	0.56*	0.65*	-	-	-	-	-0.43**
$\log(Q_{hd})$	-	-	-	0.51**	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
$\log(Q_M)$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
$\log(Q_{ma})$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
$\log(Q_{mb})$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
% Q_L	-	-0.54**	-0.52**	-0.66***	-	-0.26***	-	-	-0.63***	-0.68***	-0.59*	-	-0.56***
% Q_H	-	0.59**	0.58***	0.68***	0.27**	0.36***	-	0.73***	0.75***	0.70**	0.70**	0.63***	0.63***
% Q_{mh}	-	0.63**	0.58***	0.62***	0.18*	0.33***	0.61**	-	0.73***	0.76***	0.73***	0.17*	0.17*
% Q_{hd}	-	-	-	0.40**	-	0.20**	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
% Q_M	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
% Q_{ma}	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
% Q_{mb}	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

317 - Non-significant correlation ($p > 0.05$).
 318 * Significant at $p \leq 0.05$.
 319 ** Significant at $p \leq 0.01$.
 320 *** Significant at $p \leq 0.001$.
 321

322 The errors (averages and percentages) decreased from Category 5 to Category 1, as
323 presented in Tables 1 and 2. Categories 1 and 2 are the main roads of the city and,
324 therefore, represent high traffic flow (light and heavy vehicles). However, Categories 4
325 and 5 represent residential roads, where there is low flow of vehicles. Thus, the increase
326 in light vehicle flow in Talca and Moraleja leads to a reduction in errors owing to the
327 overestimation in the XPS 31-133 method, as presented in Table 5 under the general
328 results. In addition, this general decrease (without distinction by road category) occurs
329 for the increase in the flow of heavy vehicles in Moraleja. Therefore, the results presented
330 in Tables 1, 2, and 4 are consistent.

331 Considering those sound sources that produce an increase in the positive errors,
332 heavy traffic indicates a significant correlation. The increase in heavy traffic flow
333 produces an increase in the errors of overestimation in the XPS 31-133 method in
334 Categories 2 and 4 in Talca and Categories 1 and 2 in Moraleja. However, the effect of
335 heavy traffic on the overestimation of noise levels in the different road categories is more
336 evident when its percentage is analysed. A high flow of heavy traffic can also lead to a
337 high flow of light traffic, which occurs on the main roads in the cities (Categories 1 and
338 2). Therefore, the possible effect of heavy traffic on the positive error can be masked by
339 the increase in light traffic.

340 The effect of the percentage of heavy traffic on positive errors in the XPS 31-133
341 method, in general, is also considered. As the percentage of heavy and light traffic is
342 related, an increase in one indicates a decrease in the other. For this reason, the percentage
343 of light vehicles is negatively correlated.

344 Considering heavy vehicles, medium heavy vehicles are responsible for a significant
345 correlation with positive errors for most road categories. The overestimation of the sound
346 levels emitted by medium heavy vehicles in the XPS 31-133 method may have been one

347 of the reasons why the CNOSSOS-EU method differentiates between the two types of
 348 heavy vehicles. In fact, the medium heavy vehicles modelled by the CNOSSOS-EU
 349 method are those that presented the largest differences with respect to the heavy vehicles
 350 modelled by XPS 31-133 [39]. These differences are even larger when the percentage of
 351 heavy vehicles increases.

352 Powered two-wheelers had no significant correlation with the positive errors in both
 353 the cities. Therefore, the sound level of the motorcycles was not overestimated by the
 354 XPS 31-133 method.

355 The relationships among the negative errors obtained using the XPS 31-133 method
 356 (underestimation) and the road traffic variables are presented in Table 5. A significant
 357 correlation exists among the medium heavy vehicles and negative errors in Talca city.
 358 However, in this case, the increase in the flow and percentage of medium heavy vehicles
 359 leads to a decrease in the underestimation errors in the XPS method in Categories 1–4.
 360 These results are related to those presented in Table 4. When the XPS 31-133 method
 361 produces underestimation errors, the increase in medium heavy vehicles reduces this
 362 negative error because this method overestimates the sound levels of these vehicles.

363 **Table 5**

364 Relationship among positive uncertainties in XPS 31-133 method and flow of various
 365 vehicle types recorded under each type of road category

Pearson's <i>r</i>	Variable 1: Negative Error											
	Road categories in Talca						Road categories in Moraleja					
	1	2	3	4	5	Overall	1	2	3	4	5	Overall
$\log(Q_L)$	-	-	-	-	-	-	n.d.	-	-	-	-	-
$\log(Q_H)$	-	-	-	-	-	-	n.d.	-	-	-	-	-
$\log(Q_{mh})$	-	0.61*	0.34*	0.53*	-	0.24*	n.d.	0.65*	-	-	-	-
$\log(Q_{hd})$	-	-	-	-	-	-	n.d.	-	-	-	-	-
$\log(Q_M)$	-	-	-	-	-	-	n.d.	-	-	-	-	-
$\log(Q_{ma})$	-	-	-	-	-	-	n.d.	-	-	-	-	-
$\log(Q_{mb})$	-	-	-	-	-	-	n.d.	-	-	-	-	-
% Q_L	-	-	-	-	-	-	n.d.	-	-	-	-	-
% Q_H	-	-	-	0.40*	-	-	n.d.	-	-	-	-	-
% Q_{mh}	0.47**	0.68**	0.58***	0.43**	-	0.17*	n.d.	-	-	-	-	-
% Q_{hd}	-	-	-	-	-	-	n.d.	-	-	-	-	-

% Q_M	-	-	-0.32*	-	-	-	n.d.	-	-	-	-0.48*	-
% Q_{ma}	-	-	-	-	-	-	n.d.	-	-	-	-	-
% Q_{mb}	-	-	-0.32*	-0.34*	-	-	n.d.	-	-	-	-0.42*	-

366
367
368
369
370
371

n.d. No data
- Non-significant correlation ($p > 0.05$).
* Significant at $p \leq 0.05$.
** Significant at $p \leq 0.01$.
*** Significant at $p \leq 0.001$.

372 Further, Table 5 presents significant relationships among two-wheelers and negative
373 errors. The increase in two-wheelers, primarily motorcycles, produces an increase in the
374 negative errors in Categories 3 and 4 in Talca and Category 5 in Moraleja. The negative
375 effects of motorcycles are widespread in countries with a Mediterranean climate [40].
376 These motorcycles often have manipulated exhausts and produce noise above the
377 permitted sound level. The underestimation of motorcycle noise in the XPS 31-133
378 method seems to be more noticeable on roads with lower vehicle flow.

379 Finally, the uncertainties in the CNOSSOS method were analysed, as presented in
380 Table 6. Only the results obtained for the negative errors are presented in Table 6.
381 Categories 1, 2, and 3 in Talca and Categories 1 and 2 in Moraleja did not record positive
382 errors. The remaining categories also did not record significant correlations between the
383 positive errors and road traffic variables.

384 **Table 6**

385 Relationship among negative uncertainties in CNOSSOS-EU method and flow of various
386 vehicle types recorded under each type of road category

Pearson's r	Variable 1: Negative Error											
	Road categories in Talca						Road categories in Moraleja					
	1	2	3	4	5	Overall	1	2	3	4	5	Overall
$\log(Q_L)$	-0.44*	-0.63***	-	-	-	-0.19***	-	-	-	-	-	-0.45***
$\log(Q_H)$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
$\log(Q_{mh})$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
$\log(Q_{hd})$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
$\log(Q_M)$	-	-0.38*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
$\log(Q_{ma})$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
$\log(Q_{mb})$	-	-0.38*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
% Q_L	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
% Q_H	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
% Q_{mh}	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

% Q_{hd}	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
% Q_M	-	-	-	-0.21*	-	-	-0.51*	-0.19*	-	-	-	-
% Q_{ma}	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
% Q_{mb}	-	-	-	-0.20*	-	-	-0.54*	-	-	-	-	-

387 - Non-significant correlation ($p > 0.05$).

388 * Significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

389 *** Significant at $p \leq 0.001$.

390 The effect of heavy traffic on errors in the CNOSSOS-EU method is not significant.
391 Only Category 2 presents a significant correlation in Talca, but with a p -value ≤ 0.05 .
392 This relationship may be affected by the high flow of vehicles in Categories 1 and 2.
393 Therefore, the differentiation of heavy vehicles into two types may be a solution to avoid
394 the overestimation of these vehicles.

395 Categories 1 and 2 presented the highest average errors in the CNOSSOS method
396 (see Tables 1 and 2). Cars in Talca and motorcycles in Moraleja are strongly related to
397 underestimation errors when this method is used. However, this underestimation seems
398 to be more related to the flow than to the vehicle type. The CNOSSOS-EU propagation
399 model divides noise sources into corresponding point sources and generates point-to-
400 point estimations considering the distance between the point source and the receiver
401 [10,11]. Therefore, a spherical divergence attenuation is considered for these urban roads
402 with high vehicle flows. The operational characteristics of vehicles (speed, acceleration,
403 etc.) are fairly constant on main roads. Vehicle density and proximity to each other on
404 these roads could be influencing the propagation of sound levels. Perhaps, divergence
405 attenuation is better fitted to a linear source under these conditions. Therefore, the
406 decrease in sound levels with distance would be smaller than a spherical source and could
407 contribute to decreasing uncertainty.

408 4. Conclusions

409 A large number of sampling points and sound measurements (216 sampling points
410 and 555 sound measurements) were performed on various types of urban roads in two

411 cities of different countries to analyse the estimates obtained using the XPS 31-133 and
412 CNOSSOS-EU calculation methods. The following conclusions have been drawn as a
413 result of this study.

414 Both calculation methods provide a good estimate of the noise levels registered on
415 different types of urban roads. Moreover, the uncertainties are similar even though this
416 study was conducted in two cities of different size and location. Therefore, these noise
417 models can be applied in non-European countries and in small cities.

418 The uncertainty bias is different according to the calculation method. The XPS 31-
419 133 method tends to overestimate the noise values, whereas the CNOSSOS method tends
420 to underestimate them. When considering urban road types, the XPS-133 method has a
421 higher overestimation error for residential streets. However, the CNOSSOS method has
422 a higher underestimation error on main streets. Therefore, calibration points should be
423 considered on these types of urban roads.

424 Analysing the relationships between road traffic and the uncertainties in the
425 calculation methods, a positive effect of heavy vehicles is observed on the overestimation
426 made by the XPS 31-133 method. Medium heavy vehicles have the greatest influence on
427 this overestimation. Differentiation of sound power between medium heavy-duty
428 vehicles and heavy-duty vehicles could improve the estimates.

429 Motorcycles have a significant effect on the underestimation of noise levels in the
430 XPS 31-133 method on residential streets. Manipulated motorcycles are common in
431 Mediterranean countries.

432 The increase in light vehicles flow significantly influences the underestimation error
433 of the CNOSSOS-EU method. Uncertainty on main urban roads could perhaps be
434 decreased if these roads with high vehicle flow were considered as linear rather than
435 point sources in their divergence attenuation.

436 Despite the limitations of this study as it was carried out in small and medium-sized
437 cities and in different countries, the large number of points sampled in different types of
438 urban roads provides relevant information for the application and validation of these
439 calculation methods in any agglomeration.

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Author Statements:

Guillermo Rey Gozalo: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Resources, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Valentín**

Gómez Escobar: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Resources, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.